

ANNEX

Annex 1. Overheating increase for Living room comfort condition during 24 hours

Fig. A1. Overheating increase (hours per year) caused by renovations for Living rooms ($T > 28^{\circ}\text{C}$) during the 24h by climatic zones defined on the NBC.

Annex 2. Overheating increase for Bedrooms room comfort condition during the night

Fig. A2. Overheating increase (hours per year) caused by renovations for Bedrooms ($T > 26\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) during the night (22:00–7:00) by climatic zones defined on the NBC.

Annex 3. Geographical analysis of overheating for Living room and Bedroom conditions

Fig. A3. Geographical distribution of the total overheating in baseline scenario for Living rooms ($T > 28^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the 24h) (a) and for Bedrooms ($T > 26^{\circ}\text{C}$ during from 22:00 to 7:00) (b), and overheating increase in the scenario of complete renovation at NBC level scenario for Living rooms ($T > 28^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the 24h) (c) and for Bedrooms ($T > 26^{\circ}\text{C}$ during from 22:00 to 7:00) (d).

Annex 4. Geographical evaluation of overheating vulnerability

Fig. A4. Geographical distribution of Overheating vulnerability factor considering the scenario of complete renovation at NBC level for the comfort condition for Living rooms ($T > 28^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the 24h) (a) and for Bedrooms ($T > 26^{\circ}\text{C}$ during from 22:00 to 7:00) (b).